

ANALYSIS OF SPEECH ACTS IN THE SHORT STORIES BY MARK TWIN

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Abstract: This research focuses on pragmatics, with a particular emphasis on speech acts and their classification based on Searle's theory. The research gives numerous vivid examples complemented by detailed explanations to assist a full comprehension of the issue. The purpose of this research is to define speech acts and their classification and their analysis in Mark Twain's short stories

Key words: speech acts, assertives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declaratives

Annotatsiya: Bu tadqiqot asosiy e'tiborni pragmatikaga qaratadi, bunda alohida nutq aktlari va ularning Searl nazariyasiga asoslangan tasnifiga murojaat qiladi. Tadqiqot muammoni to'liq tushunishga yordam beradigan batafsil tushuntirishlar bilan to'ldirilgan ko'plab yorqin misollarni beradi. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi nutq aktlari, ularning tasnifini aniqlash va ularning Mark Tveyn hikoyalarida ishlatilishini tadqiq etishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: nutq aktlari, assertivlar, direktivalar, komissivlar, ekspressivlar va deklarativlar.

INTRODUCTION

The speech act expresses the communicative intention of speech participants in the communication process and the ways of its expression, the relevance of the speech situation to the topic and the forms of communication. The essence of this theory is that linguistic thought is not only to describe the events that take place in the world and interpret them as false or true, but also to react to these events, thereby studying the process aimed at achieving certain verbal goals and actions. The importance of

understanding the various aspects of speech acts is a must, so that communication can be well established. The existence of understanding between the speaker and the listener is a very important thing that will indicate that the communication is running smoothly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

People are required both to acquire the language and to have the knowledge to use the language in order to communicate. The appropriate use of the speech act acquired through the experiences within the culture is extremely important in the embodiment of the social relationships. Therefore, studying speech act is very important because everyone concern with linguistics communication in everyday life. Studying types of speech acts are usually important for solving problems faced by people in different speech situations with communication. However, knowing what kind of speech act strategies are used in language itself is also determines the success of conversation.

Studying and classification of speech acts in linguistics is directly related to the names of J.L. Austin, J.R. Searle, J. Mey and G. Yule. The concept of speech act is firstly developed by a philosopher John L. Austin in his book *How to Do Things with Words*. Austin defines speech act, as the action performed by language to modify the state of the object on which the action is performed. The writer represents an action effectively fulfilled by a sentence. John Searle undertook to develop the theory to render it more systematic. According to Searle studying speech acts is not a non-sense, the reason for concentrating on the study of speech acts is simply this and every linguistic communication involves linguistic acts.

One basic classification system, according to Yule lists five sorts of general functions provided by speech acts: declarations, representatives, expressive, directives, and commissives. Declarations are verbal acts that, via their utterance, transform the world. Representatives are speech acts that state whether the speaker believes something to be true or not. Speech acts that express how the speaker feels are known as expressives. Directives are speech acts used by a speaker to persuade someone else

to do something. They express the speaker's desires. Commands, orders, requests, and proposals are all examples. Commissives are speech acts in which the speaker expresses a willingness to take a specific action in the future. There are several resources available to help you get clarity and a better understanding, and there is scientifically proven classification of speech summarized by which is also beneficial to chat the meaning of speech act.

In Uzbek linguistics some researchers devote their works learning speech act theory and its types from different aspects. They are Sh. Safarov, M. Hakimov, M. Kurbanova, M. Gazieva. The problems of speech acts are studied by the Uzbek linguist Sh. Safarov in his book —Pragmalinguistics. Although scientist critically examines the theory, he highly values the role of speech act in pragma-linguistics doctrine. He analyzes the views of linguists on the speech acts and enriches the information of this theory with new knowledge. According to Sh. Safarov speech act is a linguistic appeal of a speaker to a listener in a specific environment with a specific purpose .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Searle's speech act theory is one of the most widely used and influential frameworks for analyzing speech acts. According to Searle, there are five main types of speech acts , which are described below with examples:

Assertives are speech acts that commit the speaker to the truth of a proposition. In other words, they are statements that are intended to convey information. Examples of assertives include:

"The bird is on the table."

"It is snowing outside."

"The football match starts at 7 pm."

Directives are speech acts that are intended to get the hearer to do something. They can take the form of orders, requests, or advice. Examples of directives include:

"Close the window, please."

"Can you pass the teapot?"

"You should see the dentist."

Commissives are speech acts that commit the speaker to a future course of action. They involve making a promise or vow to do something in the future. Examples of commissives include:

"I promise to go there on time."

"I swear I will never do it again."

"I will call you back tomorrow."

Expressives are speech acts that express the speaker's psychological state, such as their feelings or attitudes. They are often used to convey thanks, apologies, congratulations, or sympathy. Examples of expressives include:

"Thank you for your advice."

"I'm sorry for breaking your mug."

"Congratulations on your success."

Declaratives are speech acts that bring about a new state of affairs, usually through the authority of the speaker. They are often used in official contexts, such as in the pronouncement of marriage or the declaration of war. Examples of declaratives include:

"I now pronounce you husband and wife."

"I hereby declare this meeting adjourned."

"I name this ship the Queen Mary."

Searle's theory classifies speech acts into five main categories: assertives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declaratives. Each type of speech act serves a different function and is used in different contexts. Understanding these categories can help us better analyze and interpret the meaning of utterances in communication.

"The Celebrated Jumping Frog of Calaveras County" is a short story by Mark Twain that features a narrator who encounters a man named Simon Wheeler, who tells him a story about a frog jumping contest. The story can be analyzed through Searle's classification of speech acts, as follows:

Assertives:

Simon Wheeler makes several assertive speech acts throughout the story, including:

"I don't see no p'intn about that frog that's any better'n any other frog" (this statement commits him to the truth that there is nothing special about the frog in question).

"Dan'l Webster got him by the hind leg and held on till he cal'lated the feller had had enough" (this statement commits him to the truth that the frog named Dan'l Webster won the contest).

Expressives:

There are a few expressive speech acts in the story, including:

"Well, I don't see no p'intn about that frog that's any better'n any other frog" (this statement expresses Simon Wheeler's skeptical attitude towards the frog).

"I should judge he had been eatin' raw pork" (this statement expresses the narrator's disgust towards the frog's appearance).

In Mark Twain's "How to Tell a Story" used speech acts can be analyzed according to Searle's classification, which includes five categories: assertives, directives, commissives, expressives, and declaratives.

"I do not claim that I can tell a story as it ought to be told. I only claim to know how a story ought to be told, for I have been almost daily in the company of the most expert story-tellers for many years."

In this example, the speaker uses a directive to encourage the listener to pay attention to his advice on how to tell a story effectively.

"Select a few [stories] which are clean, or as nearly so as they can be gotten, and as fair to different kinds of people and sects and nationalities as possible, and put in the rest of the evening telling them yourself."

In this example, the speaker makes a commissive by suggesting that the listener should select and tell clean and fair stories to a diverse audience.

"The pause is an exceedingly important feature in any kind of story, and a frequently recurring feature, too."

In this example, the speaker uses an expressive to convey the importance of the pause in a humorous story.

"The humorous story is strictly a work of art - high and delicate art - and only an artist can tell it."

In this example, the speaker makes a declarative by stating that the humorous story is a work of art and can only be told by an artist.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is seen that all existing theories of both foreign and domestic scientists referred to speech act and its classification reveal direct relationship between a structure and a function of speech act. Their theories have unfolded some hidden aspects of speech act field theory, general characteristics of it and all proposed classifications of several scholars relatively to the theory of speech acts and, at the same time, it also inspires the researchers and readers to research in this special field. The story "The Celebrated Jumping Frog of Calaveras County" contains mainly assertive and expressive speech acts, while "How to Tell a Story" declarative, expressive, commissive, and directive speech acts are used. These speech acts serve to convey information about the story's characters, events, and setting, and to express the characters' attitudes and emotions.

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